

JOB STRESS DUE TO PHYSIOLOGICAL PRESSURE: A CASE STUDY OF EMPLOYEES OF WATER RESOURCE DEPARTMENT, GOVERNMENT OF ODISHA

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Abstract:

Objectives: *The life style of employees in various organizations i.e., government or private has become stressful in the present scenario. The private organizations are doing hard work to survive and sustain in the extremely competitive business environment. The government organizations are also no more silent spectators, because the heads of departments of various government organizations are creating a new work culture which helps the employees to perform better in their present jobs. The employees of Government organizations are not getting leisure time as they have to compete with the private organizations. Because of tremendous job pressure, the people are suffering from various physiological and psychological diseases like high blood pressure, headaches and backaches, heart ailments, anxiety and depression etc. the life of ease, relaxation and recreation is becoming obsolete day by day for the employees. The people (both technical and non-technical) of water resources department, Government of Odisha are doing a variety of jobs in the head office in Bhubaneswar and other areas of the state. The objective of this paper is to find out the stressors /reasons of physiological stress of the employees of water resource department. The secondary objective is to highlight on high blood pressure as one of the most critical symptoms of stress and to what extent it exists among the employees of water resource department.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The present paper is based on primary data collected from the employees of water resource department through questionnaire and personal interview. The secondary data was also collected from various books, journals and internet regarding the topic.*

Findings: *High blood pressure exists among the employees irrespective of age and sex. That means high blood pressure as a symptom of stress can affect people of any age i.e., young, middle age and old. High blood pressure can also affect people of any sex i.e., male or female.*

Practical Implication: *this paper will be immensely helpful to the employees of government departments in general and water resources department in particular to investigate the physiological causes of stress and formulate the strategies to cope with the stress.*

Originality/Value: *the paper contains the empirical data about the physiological symptoms of stress taking two important variables such as age and sex which will contribute for behavioral research related to stress.*

Key Words: *Stress, Stressors, work culture, competitive environment, coping strategies.*

Introduction:

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We all sometimes talk about stress and feeling stressed, usually when we feel we have too much to do and too much on our minds or other people are making unreasonable demands on us or we are dealing with situations that we do not have control over.

Stress is not a medical diagnosis, but severe stress that continues, for a long time may lead to a diagnosis of depression or anxiety or more severe mental health problems. One can reduce the effects of stress by being more conscious of the things that cause it and learning to handle those better using relaxation techniques as well as their lifestyle changes.

Situations which are recognized to be very stressful are associated with change and with lack of control over what is happening. Some of the causes of stress are happy events, but because they bring big changes or make unusual demands, they can still be stressful.

Some of the most stressful events are moving house, getting married, having a baby, bereavement, serious illness in yourself or a friend or family member. Stress is also caused by long-term difficult circumstances such as unemployment, poverty, relationship problems, caring for a disabled family member or friend, difficulties and work, bad housing, noisy neighbours.

Stress can have a positive side. A certain level of stress may be necessary and enjoyable in order to help to prepare for something or to actually do it e.g. taking part in a performance, taking an examination or doing an important piece of work for a deadline. It will be stressful even if it is enjoyed and the stress itself will keep you alert and focused.

Objectives of the study:

1. The objective of this study is to find out the weather excessive physiological pressure or demand on the job causes stress or not.
2. The objective is also to find out the relationship between physiological pressure and job stress.

Scope of the study:

The scope of the study is confined to the Department of Water Resource, Government of Odisha, Bhubaneswar.

Literature Review:

The International Labour Organization (ILO) 1986 defines psychological hazards in terms of the interactions among job content, work organization and management environmental and organizational conditions as well as the employees competencies and needs. Those interactions which may prove hazardous, influence employees health through their perceptions and experiences. Whilst this definition is consistent with transactional models of stress, it strongly associates exposure to psychological stressors with experience of stress. It may be argued that psychological hazards may have direct effects on the person; effect which are not mediated by the experience of stress.

Cox and Griffith (1995) provide an alternative definition of psychological hazards. They define psychological hazards as ‘those aspects of work design and the organization and management of work and their social and environmental contexts, which have the potential for causing psychological, social or physical harm;.

With the emergence of psychosocial work environment research and occupational psychology in the 1960’s (Johnson and Hall, 1996) the focus of interest has moved away from the traditional individual perspective and towards considering the impact of certain aspects of the work environment on health.

There is consensus among the various attempts to review literature on those psychological hazards of work which are experienced as stressful and otherwise carry the potential for harm. (Baker, 1985, Cooper and Marshall, 1976;

Cox and Cox 1993; Frankenhauser and Gardell 1976, Karasek and Therell 1990, Marmot and Madge, 1987; Sharit and Salvendy 1982). This consensus is summarized in ten different categories of job characteristics, work environments and organizations which may be hazardous and these categories relate to either the work context or the work content. These include organizational culture and function; role in organization, career development; decision control, interpersonal relationships at work, home – work interface, work environment and work equipment, task design, workload / work pace and work schedule.

Research Methodology

Sources of study:

The source of data collection was both primary and secondary. The primary data were collected through questionnaire and the secondary data were collected from related research works, published books, journals etc.

Sample Size:

The sample size consists of 60 respondents of Water Resource Department, Bhubaneswar, and Government of Odisha. The respondents are categorized into various categories such as age, occupation, gender, educational qualification, experience, physical pressure causing illness and diseases.

Period of the study:

Data was collected through structured questionnaire during the period of study directly communicating with the respondents.

Methods of Analysis:

The data and other related information collected are classified, tabulated and processed and their findings are presented in a systematic manner. Statistical tools, chi-square test are used to test the hypothesis.

Hypothesis of study:

1. Age and High Blood pressure are independent to each other.
2. Gender and High Blood pressure are independent to each other.

Age:

H₀ (Null Hypothesis): Age of the employees and High Blood Pressure are independent to each other.

Age	20 – 30	30 – 40	40 – 50	50 – 60	Total
Yes	0	0	7	8	15
No	2	3	16	24	45
Total	2	3	23	32	60

$$E_{11} = \frac{15 \times 2}{60} = 0.5$$

$$E_{12} = \frac{15 \times 3}{60} = 0.75$$

$$E_{13} = \frac{15 \times 23}{60} = 5.75$$

$$E_{14} = \frac{15 \times 32}{60} = 8$$

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$$E_{21} = \frac{45 \times 2}{60} = 1.5$$

$$E_{22} = \frac{45 \times 3}{60} = 2.25$$

$$E_{23} = \frac{45 \times 23}{60} = 17.25$$

$$E_{24} = \frac{45 \times 32}{60} = 24$$

O	E	(O - E)	(O - E) ²	(O - E) ² /E
0	0.5	- 0.5	0.25	0.5
0	0.75	- 0.75	0.5625	0.75
7	5.75	1.25	1.5625	0.271739
8	8.0	0	0	0
2	1.5	0.5	0.25	0.1667
3	2.25	0.75	0.5625	0.25
16	17.25	- 1.25	1.5625	0.09058
24	24.0	0	0	0

Total Calculated Value

2.028986

$$V = (r - 1)(c - 1) = (2 - 1)(4 - 1) = 1 \times 3 = 3$$

Total value of 5% level of significance is 7.81

$$TV = 7.81 > CV$$

H₀ is not rejected, so age and high blood pressure are independent to each other.

Gender:

H₀ (Null Hypothesis): Gender of the employees and High Blood Pressure are independent to each other.

Gender	Male	Female	Total
Yes	13	0	13
No	44	3	47
Total	57	3	60

$$E_{11} = \frac{RT \times CT}{47} = \frac{13 \times 57}{47} = 12.35$$

$$E_{12} = \frac{13 \times 3}{60} = 0.65$$

$$E_{21} = \frac{47 \times 57}{60} = 44.65$$

$$E_{22} = \frac{47 \times 3}{60} = 2.35$$

O	E	(O – E)	(O – E) ²	(O – E) ² /E
13	12.35	0.65	0.4225	0.034211
0	0.65	-0.65	0.4225	0.65
44	44.65	-0.65	0.4225	0.009462
3	2.35	0.65	0.4225	0.179787
			CV =	0.87346

$$V = (r - 1) (c - 1) = (2 - 1) (2 - 1) = 1 \times 1 = 1$$

$$TV = 3.84 > CV$$

H₀ is not rejected, so gender and high blood pressure are independent to each other.

Findings and Conclusion:

Finding of the data analysis (study) and conclusion are summarized as follows:

1. Age and high blood pressure are independent to each other, that means high blood pressure as a symptom of stress can affect people of any age i.e., young, middle aged and old.
2. Gender and high blood pressure are independent to each other, that means high blood pressure as a symptom of stress can affect people of any gender i.e., male or female.
3. High blood pressure is a symptom of stress. People suffering from high blood pressure take excessive psychological demand or pressure related to job.

Reference:

1. Hardy GE, Interventions for work stress
2. Grimshaw. J, Employment and Health Psychological stress in the workplace
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